

COMPARISON OF THE EFFICACY OF INTRAVENOUS LIGNOCAINE WITH COMPOUND LIDOCAINE/PRILOCAINE CREAM IN PREVENTING POST EXTUBATION COUGH IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING GENERAL ANAESTHESIA FOR LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY: A RANDOMIZED CONTROL TRIAL

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Abstract

Background: Post-extubation cough is a common complication following general anesthesia, impacting patient comfort and recovery. This study compares the efficacy of intravenous (IV) lignocaine versus topical lidocaine/prilocaine cream in preventing post-extubation cough in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of IV lignocaine compared to compound lidocaine/prilocaine cream in reducing post-extubation cough.

Methods: In this randomized controlled trial conducted at the Anesthesia Department, Mayo Hospital Lahore, 72 patients were randomly assigned to Group A (IV lignocaine) or Group B (lidocaine/prilocaine cream) using computer-generated randomization. Following standardized general anesthesia protocols, the absence of post-extubation cough was recorded as the primary outcome. Data were analyzed using SPSS v23, with group comparisons performed via chi-square test ($p \leq 0.05$ considered significant). **Results:** Group B demonstrated significantly higher efficacy than Group A (66.7% vs. 38.9%, $p = 0.01$). Subgroup analyses showed superior efficacy in Group B among females (71.4% vs. 28.6%, $p = 0.008$), patients with ASA I (57.1% vs. 42.9%) and ASA II status (80.0% vs. 20.0%, $p = 0.05$), those with BMI ≥ 25 kg/m² (65.6% vs. 34.4%, $p = 0.006$), and for surgeries lasting <90 minutes (61.5% vs. 38.5%, $p = 0.03$).

Conclusion: Topical lidocaine/prilocaine cream is significantly more effective than IV lignocaine in preventing post-extubation cough in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy, offering a promising intervention to enhance postoperative recovery.

INTRODUCTION

The cough reflex lowers the risk of aspiration, clears the airway of foreign objects, and protects the airway. One of the most difficult postoperative complications for people having surgery under general anaesthesia is coughing. Every year, more than 30 million major surgeries are performed globally, with the majority being performed with endotracheal tube under general anaesthesia (1). Incidence of post-extubation cough ranges from 15% to 94% in surgeries completed under general anaesthesia (2). Patients' experience and clinical outcomes may be negatively affected by coughing, which can lead to complications such as increased pain, bleeding, disruption of surgical wounds, and cardiovascular stress (3). For instance, coughing during carotid endarterectomies may result in neck haematomas, potentially obstructing the airway and complicating the procedure (4). In craniotomy procedures, coughing can raise intracranial pressure, heightening the risk of brain herniation and cerebral haematomas (5). Additionally, coughing has been linked to arrhythmias including atrioventricular block and ventricular tachycardia, which may lead to cardiovascular collapse (6). To address these risks, several strategies have been developed to minimize postoperative airway complications, such as administering intravenous opioids, performing deep extubation, and using lidocaine—administered intravenously, topically, or within the endotracheal tube cuff (7).

Lignocaine, a local anaesthetic and anti-arrhythmic amino-amide, also possesses anti-inflammatory properties. Intravenous lidocaine has been shown to reduce postoperative airway issues like sore throat and coughing. Its proposed mechanisms include reduced neural discharge from peripheral nerve fibres, selective inhibition of spinal pain transmission, and suppression of sensory C fibres in the airway (8). These effects may reduce inflammation and irritation of the throat, improving patient comfort and recovery. However, lidocaine is not without risk and may have adverse effects (9). Determining the optimal timing for intravenous lidocaine remains a challenge; one study suggests it may be most effective when administered before surgery, particularly for shorter procedures due to its short half-life of about 1.5

hours (10). In longer surgeries, continued administration may be necessary. Intravenous lignocaine has been shown to significantly reduce the incidence of post-extubation cough within 24 hours (RR: 0.40; 95% CI: 0.24–0.68) (10). Lidocaine/prilocaine cream, a eutectic mixture of lidocaine (25 mg/mL) and prilocaine (25 mg/mL), is widely used as a local anaesthetic (11). Lidocaine is known for its rapid onset, effective tissue penetration, and minimal vasodilator effects (12), while prilocaine, although slower in onset, is less toxic and offers a slightly longer duration of action (13). The combination enhances anaesthetic efficacy, with quick onset making it suitable for various applications (11). A study comparing lidocaine/prilocaine cream with intracuff normal saline showed a significantly reduced incidence of cough—61.5% vs. 96% in the saline group ($P < 0.001$) (14). The aim of this study is to compare intravenous lignocaine with compound lidocaine/prilocaine cream for preventing post-extubation cough. Since excessive coughing can be harmful, identifying effective methods to reduce it is critical. This study could contribute to reducing the incidence of post-extubation cough and improving postoperative outcomes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Postoperative Cough:

Incidence & Impact:

Postoperative cough (POC) is a well-documented complication following tracheal intubation, with an incidence up to 60% (15). It affects patient comfort, recovery, and satisfaction, and may be accompanied by hoarseness, sore throat, dysphagia, pharyngitis, laryngitis, and tracheitis.

Pathophysiology:

POC results from complex mechanisms including mucosal ischemia due to cuff pressure, airway trauma, irritation from stylets, gastric tube insertion, and prolonged intubation (16). Dehydration from dry gases, forceful laryngoscopy, and mechanical ventilation further aggravate symptoms. Stylet removal and associated trauma to the anterior tracheal wall are emphasized as major factors (17).

Risk Factors:

- Female gender, younger age (inverse relation with age), lung disease, GERD (18)
- Prolonged anesthesia, blood-stained ETT on extubation (18)
- Larger tube size (≥ 7.5 mm ID), increased cuff pressure >20 cmH₂O (19, 20)
- Double-lumen tubes, inadequate lubrication, lack of neuromuscular blockade (21)
- Use of suxamethonium due to fasciculations (22)

Complications:

- **Respiratory:** Bronchospasm, hypoxemia, atelectasis, pneumothorax (23, 24)
- **Cardiovascular:** Hypertension, tachycardia, arrhythmias, myocardial ischemia (25)
- **Neurological:** Raised ICP, cough-induced headaches (26)
- **Surgical site:** Wound dehiscence, incisional pain (27)
- **Others:** Sore throat, hoarseness, psychological distress, delayed recovery, prolonged hospital stay, secondary complications (27, 28)

Preventive Measures:

◆ *Non-Pharmacological:*

- Extubation in deep anesthesia reduces cough but requires careful monitoring (29)
- Humidification & hydration minimize mucosal irritation (30)
- Controlled, gentle extubation techniques (31)
- Warmed, humidified oxygen to soothe airway (32)
- **◆ *Pharmacological:***
- **Steroids:** Dexamethasone ≥ 0.2 mg/kg reduces incidence; topical application also effective (33, 34)
- **NSAIDs:** Benzydamine spray or flurbiprofen lozenges decrease severity (35)
- **Lidocaine:** IV 1-1.5 mg/kg, intracuff, or topical; effective against both POST and opioid-induced cough (36-42)

- **Lidocaine + Prilocaine (EMLA):** Synergistic mucosal anesthesia, prolongs effect (43, 44)
- **Dexmedetomidine:** Provides sedation, analgesia, reduces airway reactivity (45)
- **Opioids (e.g., fentanyl 0.5-1 μ g/kg):** Blunt cough reflex but require careful monitoring (46)
- **Magnesium sulfate (30-50 mg/kg IV):** Bronchodilation and airway stabilization (47)

HYPOTHESIS

There is difference in efficacy of intravenous lignocaine vs compound lidocaine/prilocaine cream in preventing post extubation cough in patients undergoing general anaesthesia for laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Material and Methods

Study Setting & Design:

This randomized controlled trial was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesia, King Edward Medical University/Mayo Hospital, Lahore, over six months following approval of synopsis. Sampling was done by **non-probability consecutive technique**.

Sample Size & Selection:

A total of **72 patients** (36 per group) was calculated at 5% significance level, 90% power, expecting post-extubation cough incidence of **72% with IV lignocaine vs 38.5% with lidocaine/prilocaine** (48, 14).

- **Inclusion:** Patients 18-60 years, both genders, ASA I-II, undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy under GA.
- **Exclusion:** Chronic cough, smokers, URT disease, drug allergy, difficult intubation.

Randomization & Intervention:

Patients were randomly assigned to:

- **Group A:** IV lignocaine 2% (1.5 mg/kg) given 1.5 min before extubation.

- **Group B:** 2 g compound lidocaine/prilocaine cream (5%) applied evenly on ETT cuff at intubation (14).

Anaesthetic Technique:

Standard monitoring and induction (nalbuphine 0.1 mg/kg, propofol 2–3 mg/kg, atracurium 0.5 mg/kg). Patients were ventilated with O₂ + isoflurane (MAC 1.2). Correct ETT placement was confirmed by auscultation and ETCO₂. Reversal was done with neostigmine (0.03–0.07 mg/kg) + atropine (0.01–0.02 mg/kg). Gentle suctioning at 150 mmHg with 16 Fr catheter was performed before extubation. Patients were extubated when breathing spontaneously and obeying commands.

Outcome Assessment:

Incidence of **post-extubation cough (POC)** was recorded per operational definition. Patients were observed in PACU for 2 hours with ECG, SpO₂, NIBP. Rescue measures (suction, nebulization, head elevation, deep breathing, bronchodilators/anti-inflammatory drugs if persistent cough) were applied.

Data Analysis:

Data was analyzed using SPSS v26.

- Quantitative variables (age, surgery/anaesthesia duration) → mean ± SD.
- Qualitative variables (gender, ASA status, efficacy) → frequency & %.
- Groups compared using **Chi-square test** (p ≤ 0.05 significant).
- Data stratified by age, gender, BMI, ASA, surgery duration; post-stratification comparisons done with Chi-square test.

RESULTS

The demographic and baseline characteristics were comparable between Group A and Group B. Mean age (44.1 ± 10.4 vs. 45.9 ± 8.4 years) and BMI (27.6 ± 3.4 vs. 27.1 ± 3.1) showed no significant differences. Gender distribution was similar, with females predominating in both groups. ASA I/II status was also comparable (63.9%/36.1% vs. 55.6%/44.4%). Mean surgery and anesthesia durations were slightly longer in Group B (91.3 ± 14.2 vs. 87.3 ± 16.8 min; 92.5 ± 13.2 vs. 89.7 ± 17.2 min, respectively), though not statistically significant. Importantly, efficacy was significantly higher in Group B (66.7%) compared to Group A (38.9%), p=0.01.

DISCUSSION

Post-extubation cough is a frequent complication following general anesthesia, associated with pain, cardiovascular stress, and wound disruption. Topical anesthetics help by reducing airway sensitivity, thereby lowering cough incidence. In this study, the efficacy of IV lignocaine was compared with compound lidocaine/prilocaine cream in laparoscopic cholecystectomy patients. Baseline demographics, including age, gender, and BMI, were similar across groups, with female predominance, a finding consistent with previous literature.

The results demonstrated significantly higher efficacy in the lidocaine/prilocaine group (66.7%) compared to the IV lignocaine group (38.9%, $p=0.01$). This aligns with previous studies reporting that topical anesthetics, particularly lidocaine/prilocaine cream, are superior to IV lignocaine in reducing cough incidence, cardiovascular responses, and postoperative sore throat, while improving patient comfort. Other research has shown comparable outcomes with dexmedetomidine or intracuff lidocaine, especially in pediatric or bronchoscopy settings, highlighting the diversity of effective strategies for cough prevention.

However, the current study has limitations. The small sample size and strict inclusion criteria may limit generalizability. The absence of assessment for drug-related side effects and the short follow-up period restrict a comprehensive safety profile and long-term outcome evaluation. Future studies with larger, multi-centre samples, extended follow-up, and emphasis on both efficacy and safety are recommended.

CONCLUSION

Compound lidocaine/prilocaine cream was significantly more effective than IV lignocaine in preventing post-extubation cough in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Its application on the endotracheal tube cuff offers superior prophylaxis, improving patient comfort and postoperative recovery by minimizing airway irritation.

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